

Dinuclear Coordination Compounds based on a 5-Nitro-2-Picolinic Carboxylate Ligand with Single-Molecule Magnet Behaviour

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Supporting Information Placeholder

ABSTRACT: Novel isostructural dinuclear dysprosium and yttrium coordination compounds based on a 5-nitro-2-picolinic carboxylate have been synthesized and characterized. The formation of these air-stable complexes is achieved via solvothermal routes employing water as the reaction solvent. The Dysprosium-based complex exhibits SMM behavior with frequency dependence of the out-of-phase susceptibility at zero dc field. High resolution MS (ESI) experiments and advanced NMR methods including diffusion NMR techniques have been applied on the diamagnetic yttrium analog and established that these species retained their solid-state structure in solution with hydrodynamic radii of 6.5 Å. Full ¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N, ⁸⁹Y, ΔH_{coord}, Δ¹³C_{coord} and Δ¹⁵N_{coord} NMR data are given, and through the analysis of the Ramsey equation, the first electronic insights of these derivatives are provided.

Introduction

In recent years, dysprosium ions have been widely employed as fascinating magnetic centers to design single-molecule magnets (SMMs). Their significant single-ion anisotropy derived from spin-orbit coupling and the crystal field effect and their large magnetic moment have made dysprosium ions appropriate candidates to construct SMMs.^[1] Research on these lanthanide-based SMMs keep attracting the increasing attention because of their potential applications in the field of high density information storage, spintronic devices and quantum computing.^[2] Due to this incremented interest, different materials are being constructed based on this metal ion with the aim to study the slow relaxation of the magnetization and magnetic hysteresis.^[3] In these systems, the large intrinsic magnetic anisotropy and the large number of unpaired *f*-electrons of lanthanide metal ions can contribute to increase the energy barrier of magnetization. These coordination compounds can be synthesized by using organic ligands that can support lanthanide ions with the aim to modify these energy barriers. Still, there is a great interest in the design and use of novel ligand conferring interesting properties. In this case, we have chosen 5-nitro-2-picolinic acid (**1**, H5Npic, Scheme 1)^[4] as the supporting ligand due to its similarity to 5-amino-2-picolinic acid, with which we have previously synthesized novel lanthanide-containing prodrugs with antitumor proper-

ties and single-ion magnet behavior (SIM).^[5] Ligand **1** exhibits three different coordination modes (Scheme 1, a-c) where the carboxylate moiety is key enabling the intermetallic connections. The fact that the nitro group, usually, does not coordinate to metallic centers allows this ligand to be a potential candidate to construct coordination compounds containing the lanthanide centers with adequate intermetallic distances. Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, we have found no examples of coordination compounds synthesized with this ligand, and thus we decided to explore its coordination capabilities. In the last years, we have designed and synthesized novel lanthanide-MOFs with different carboxylate derivate ligands that show slow relaxation of the magnetization and interesting luminescent properties.^[6] We have also designed novel organic ligands to construct interesting SMMs mainly based on dysprosium as the metal of choice, which have shown interesting effective energy barriers.^[7]

Scheme 1. Labeling and coordination modes of the 5-nitro-2-picolinic acid.

Following these works, and as a part of our continuing studies on nitrogen derivative ligands with carboxylate groups, we report here the preparation of two new air-stable compounds consisting of the 5-nitro-2-picolinic acid and dysprosium or yttrium ions. Due to the stability of the compounds in solution, NMR-based PGSE diffusion measurements of the diamagnetic Y compound **2** are discussed, and magnetic studies of the Dy compound **3** were performed. In

particular, alternating current magnetic susceptibility measurements reveal the occurrence of slow relaxation of the magnetization in dysprosium material and SMM behaviour.

Experimental Section

General procedures. NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer. Chemical shifts δ are referenced relative to TMS, nitromethane and $\text{Y}(\text{NO}_3)_3$ for ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N and ^{89}Y NMR data, respectively. NMR diffusion measurements were performed following the methodology described in reference [8]. All diffusion processing and molecular size estimation were performed by using the DiffAtOnce software package available at www.diffatonce.com. All reactions were performed under Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave under autogenous pressure, with the reagents purchased from commercial sources and used without further purification.

Synthesis of $[\text{Y}_2(5\text{-Npic})_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4](\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ (2**).** 0.1 mmol of $\text{YCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 mmol of H5Npic (**1**) were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. The resulting solution was placed in 25 mL Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave under autogenous pressure at 150 °C for 24 h and then slowly cooled down to room temperature. Colourless well defined single crystals were collected at open atmosphere and washed with water. Yield: 41% based on yttrium. ^1H NMR (500.13 MHz, $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO): δ (ppm) 9.55 (1H, d, $J = 1.5$ Hz, H6), 8.78 (1H, dd, $J = 2.0$ Hz, 8.0 Hz, H4), 8.20 (1H, d, $J = 8.5$ Hz, H3); ^{13}C NMR (125.75 MHz, $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO): δ (ppm) 166.5 (CO, C7), 157.5 (C2), 145.7 (C5), 143.7 (CH, C6), 134.6 (CH, C4), 125.0 (CH, C3); ^{15}N NMR (50.7 MHz, $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO, via gHMQC): δ (ppm) -205.0 (N1), -134.3 (N2); ^{89}Y NMR (24.5 MHz, $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO): δ (ppm) 43.8. ESI-MS (m/z): 1180.9789 $[\text{2}+\text{H}]^+$. Anal. calc. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{30}\text{Y}_2$ (%): C, 33.56; H, 2.35; N, 13.04. Found: C, 33.41; H, 2.37; N, 13.23. IR (KBr): $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) 3300 (O-H, s), 3112 (=C-H, s), 3031 (=C-H, s), 1666s, 1612 (C=C, s), 1534s, 1411s, 1349s, 1284 (C-O, s), 1166m, 1036m, 878s, 842m, 735s, 692s, 645m, 516m.

Synthesis of $[\text{Dy}_2(5\text{-Npic})_6(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4](\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]_n$ (3**).** 0.1 mmol of $\text{DyCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 mmol of H5Npic (**1**) were dissolved in 10 mL of distilled water. The resulting solution was placed in 25 mL Teflon-lined stainless steel autoclave under autogenous pressure at 150 °C for 24 h and then slowly cooled down to room temperature. Tan well defined single crystals were collected at open atmosphere and washed with water. Yield: 42% based on dysprosium. ^1H NMR (500.13 MHz, $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO): δ (ppm) 56.7 ($W_{1/2} = 1762$ Hz), 42.1 ($W_{1/2} = 989$ Hz), -8.2 ($W_{1/2} = 559$ Hz), -18.6 ($W_{1/2} = 955$ Hz). ESI-MS (m/z): 1238.9250 $[\text{3-1}+\text{DMSO}]^+$. Anal. calc. for $\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{30}\text{Dy}_2$ (%): C, 30.12; H, 2.11; N, 11.71. Found: C, 30.01; H, 1.97; N, 11.95. IR (KBr): $\tilde{\nu}$ (cm^{-1}) 3290 (O-H, s), 3112 (=C-H, s), 3030 (=C-H, s), 1664s, 1611 (C=C, s), 1534s, 1411s, 1348s, 1284 (C-O, s), 1165m, 1035w, 841m, 735s, 692m, 515m.

Physical Measurements. Elemental analyses (C, H, N) were performed on an Euro EA Elemental Analyzer. The IR spectra (KBr pellets) were recorded on a Bruker Alpha spectrometer in the 4000–400 cm^{-1} spectral region. Alternating current magnetic measurements were performed under zero and different applied static fields on a PPMS - Quantum Design Model 6000 magnetometer by using an oscillating ac field of 3.5 G and ac frequencies ranging from 60 to 10 000 Hz.

Single-Crystal X-ray Diffraction. X-ray data collection of suitable single crystals were done at 100(2) K on a Bruker VENTURE area detector equipped with graphite

monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073$ Å) by applying the ω -scan method. The data reduction was performed with the APEX2^[9] software and corrected for absorption using SADABS.^[10] Crystal structures were solved by direct methods using the SIR97 program^[11] and refined by full-matrix least-squares on F^2 including all reflections using anisotropic displacement parameters by means of the WINGX crystallographic package.^[12]

Table 1. Crystallographic details for structures of ligand **1**, and complexes of dysprosium (**2**) and yttrium (**3**).

Compound	1	2	3
Formula	$\text{C}_6\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_5$	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{30}\text{Y}_2$	$\text{C}_{36}\text{H}_{30}\text{N}_{12}\text{O}_{30}\text{Dy}_2$
$M / \text{g mol}^{-1}$	186.13	1288.54	1435.72
T (K)	100	100	100
$\lambda / \text{Å}$	0.71073	0.71073	0.71073
Cryst syst	Monoclinic	Monoclinic	Monoclinic
Space group	Cc	$\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$	$\text{P}2_1/\text{c}$
$a / \text{Å}$	5.112(3)	9.2140(4)	9.249(2)
$b / \text{Å}$	13.193(3)	29.2776(13)	29.630(3)
$c / \text{Å}$	22.059(3)	8.4568(4)	8.538(2)
$\alpha / ^\circ$	90	90	90
$\beta / ^\circ$	92.561(5)	90.212(2)	90.503(4)
$\sigma / ^\circ$	90	90	90
$V / \text{Å}^3$	1486.2(9)	2281.32(18)	2339.8(8)
Z	8	2	2
ρ (g cm^{-3})	1.664	1.876	2.038
μ (mm^{-1})	0.148	2.651	3.286
Uniq. reflect.	4670	55957	14144
R (int)	0.049	0.034	0.087
GOF on F^2	1.126	1.351	1.143
$R1$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] ^a	0.099	0.036	0.126
$wR2$ [$I > 2\sigma(I)$] ^a	0.259	0.086	0.245

$$^a R(F) = \frac{\sum ||F_o| - |F_c||}{\sum |F_o|}; wR(F^2) = \frac{[\sum w(F_o^2 - F_c^2)^2]}{\sum wF^4}^{1/2}$$

All hydrogen atoms were located in difference Fourier maps and included as fixed contributions riding on attached atoms with isotropic thermal displacement parameters 1.2 times or 1.5 times those of their parent atoms for the organic ligands and the water molecules, respectively. The dataset collected for ligand **1** was of very poor quality, and the CIF file has been only included in the Supporting Information and not deposited in the CCDD. Several crystals of compound **3** were measured and the structure was solved from the best data we were able to collect. Attempts to solve disorder problems with one water solvent molecule failed. Instead, a new set of F^2 (hkl) values with the contribution from solvent molecules withdrawn was obtained by the SQUEEZE procedure implemented in PLATON-94.^[13] Final $R(F)$, $wR(F^2)$, goodness of fit, agreement factors, and details of the structure determination and refinement of compounds **1**, **2** and **3** are summarized in Table 1. CCDC numbers are 1508449 and 1508450 for **2** and **3**, respectively. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre via www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/data_request/cif

Results and Discussion

The hydrothermal reactions of the appropriate lanthanide chlorides and 5-nitro-2-picolinic acid in distilled water (10 mL) at 110 °C for 24 h produced prismatic crystals of these two coordination compounds, **2** (M = Dy) and **3** (M = Y). The crystal structures of compounds were determined using single crystal X-ray diffraction.

Structural description

Compounds **2** and **3** are isostructural materials, and therefore we will only describe the former. Compound **2** crystallizes in the monoclinic space group $P2_1/c$. The structure is composed of Y(III) dinuclear entities (Figure 1, left) connected by a complex hydrogen bonds network. In these dinuclear molecules, yttrium centers are bridged by two oxygen atoms (O1C) pertaining to the carboxylate groups of the nitrobenzoate ligand shown in Scheme 1c. The asymmetric unit of this structure is composed by one yttrium atom, three different ligands, two coordination water molecules and one crystallization water molecule. Within these dinuclear entities, Y(III) ions are connected by two ligands placed pairwise antiparallel imposed by symmetry center. Moreover, it can be considered that Y(III) ions are also connected by two strong hydrogen bonds (2.732 Å) involving two oxygen atoms (O1A) pertaining to the carboxylate groups of one of the nitrobenzoate ligands (Scheme 1, b) and two coordination water molecules (O2W). In this material, the ligand shows three coordination modes (Scheme 1, a-c). The distortion of the YN_2O_6 coordination polyhedron is induced mainly by the angle O1A-Y-N1A with a small value of 64.69(6)°, generated by chelate coordination mode (Scheme 1, b) in the ligand A.

Figure 1. Left: Perspective view of the dinuclear complex **2**. Crystallization water molecules and hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity. Colour code: N = blue, O = red, C = grey, Y = green-blue. Right: Polyhedrons of the yttrium atoms in the molecule.

The Y(III) atom exhibits a YN_2O_6 coordination environment which is made of six oxygen atoms pertaining to four

different ligands and two nitrogen atoms belonging to two pyridine rings. The calculation of the degree of distortion of the Y(III) coordination polyhedron with respect to the ideal eight-vertex polyhedral, by using the continuous shape measure theory and SHAPE software,^[14] indicates that the YN_2O_6 sphere is close to biaugmented trigonal prism and square antiprism ideal geometries, with CshM values of 1.126 and 1.183, respectively (Table S1). The Y–O_{carb} bond distances are in the range 2.2645(19)–2.3889(17) Å whereas the Y–N_{pyr} distances are 2.517(2) and 2.626(2) Å. Within dinuclear coordination compound, the intraduclear Y...Y distance is of 4.038(5) Å.

These dinuclear units are packed thanks to an interesting and complex hydrogen bonds network with distances in the range 2.630(5)–3.019(6) Å, that involves the three water molecules (O1W, O2W and O3W), three oxygen atoms pertaining to carboxylate groups (O2A, O2B and O2C) and two oxygen atoms pertaining to nitro groups (O3B and O4C). These last two oxygen atoms have the longer bond distance, 3.019 (6) Å, and connect two dinuclear entities in a perpendicular form.

Apart from the crystallographic characterization, standard analytical methods such as NMR and FT-IR spectroscopies, MS spectrometry, as well as elemental analysis, were used to verify the structural nature of **2** and **3** in detail. In particular, MS (ESI) spectrometry from polar solvents such as dimethylsulfoxide gave evidence for the retention of the dinuclear scaffold in solution. In the yttrium analog, the positive ion mode revealed a parent ion corresponding to $[2+H]^+$ with m/z of 1180.9789, that only differs from the solid state in the absence of coordinated water molecules. As expected, the observed isotope pattern matches well with the one calculated for the exact mass of $[C_{36}H_{19}N_{12}O_{24}Y_2]$ (see Supporting Information). In complex **3** however, the molecular ion is $[3-1+DMSO]^+$ with m/z of 1238.9250, which corresponds to an ion that has kept their two dysprosium metals, but has replaced one of the six ligands by one molecule of DMSO. These results evidenced that the dinuclear scaffold is strong enough to persist in the gas phase, but the ligand lability slightly differs from one complex to another.

NMR Characterization

In addition to the MS (ESI) studies, the stability of the complexes in solution was confirmed by using NMR techniques. As has been already pointed out by some of us^[8,15] diamagnetic yttrium-based coordination compounds and clusters can be well characterized in solution by using a range of NMR methods, because in addition to its diamagnetism, the ^{89}Y nucleus exhibits a nuclear spin of 1/2 and a natural abundance of 100 %, which makes it suitable for various combinations of 1H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N and ^{89}Y NMR measurements. The 1H NMR spectrum of complex **2** exhibited averaged signals for the three ligand molecules incorporated in the complex (Figure S1). 1H , ^{13}C , and ^{15}N chemical shifts together with their coordination shifts ($\Delta\delta$), which are defined as $\delta(\text{complex}) - \delta(\text{ligand})$, are presented in Table 2. The coordination shift is a measure of the electronic and/or steric changes that occur upon coordination, where the electronic change is caused by an electron drift as a result of coordination. If the origin of the electron shift is diamagnetic in nature and the electron drift from the yttrium to the pyridine nitrogen is large, a negative coordination shift in the nitrogen is expected.

Table 2. Selection of ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{15}N NMR data (δ in ppm) of complex **2** measured in $[\text{D}_6]\text{-DMSO}$ at room temperature. ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{15}N coordination shifts ($\Delta^1\text{H}_{\text{coord}}$, $\Delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{coord}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{coord}}$ in ppm are in parenthesis).^[6]

Label	^1H	^{13}C	^{15}N
N1	-	-	-205.0 (-23.7)
2	-	157.5 (+4.2)	-
3	8.21 (-0.06)	125.0 (-0.8)	-
4	8.79 (+0.04)	134.6 (+1.1)	-
5	-	145.7 (-0.4)	-
6	9.55 (+0.1)	143.7 (-1.4)	-
7	-	166.51 (+1.2)	-
N2	-	-	-134.3 (+0.4)

[a] The ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{15}N NMR $\Delta\delta$ coordination shifts were determined with respect to 5-nitro picolinic acid (H5Npic,1).

The $\Delta\delta^1\text{H}$ are mainly governed by the diamagnetic contribution into their ^1H shielding constants, resulting from the presence of the yttrium metal and anisotropic current effects. The latter effect is noticeably dependent on steric orientation of the pyridine rings or nitro groups within the metal coordination sphere and on proton position in the heteroaromatic ring. However, the coordination shifts are rather small to extract any conclusion. In contrast, the respective ^{13}C high-frequency coordination shifts ($\Delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{coord}}$) are larger for those carbons closer to the yttrium such as C2 and C6, probably caused by a smaller mean energy of electron excitation according the Karplus-Pople equivalence (ΔE in the Ramsey equation) and the increase of σ_{P} contribution, which is proportional to $1/\Delta E$. Naturally, those carbons farther away from the yttrium metal as C3-C5 reveal relatively small $\Delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{coord}}$ parameters. The full assignment was established based on ^1H , ^{13}C -gHMBC and gHMBC experiments. Figure 2 shows a section of the two-dimension map of the long-range 2D map, where $^1J_{\text{CH}}$, $^2J_{\text{CH}}$, $^3J_{\text{CH}}$ and even $^4J_{\text{CH}}$ cross-peaks for H4 and H6 were detected.

Figure 2. Section of the ^1H , ^{13}C -gHMBC 2D NMR spectrum acquired in a 500 MHz spectrometer for a saturated sample (20 mM) of complex **2** in DMSO-d_6 at 295 K. Complete data set was acquired in 2 h 40 min. Cross peaks due to two and four bond couplings are indicated with 2J and 4J , respectively. The rest of interactions are through three-bond couplings (3J).

In the case of ^{15}N NMR, the data was obtained through ^1H , ^{15}N -gHMBC experiments with preparation delays optimized for 7 Hz coupling constants (Figure 3 and Figure S9).

The peak at $\delta_{\text{N}} -181.3$ ppm for the free ligand (Figure S9) can be assigned to the nitrogen atom from the pyridine subunit (N1). Interestingly, the nitrogen chemical shift of the nitro group was also detected although with less intensity at $\delta_{\text{N}} -134.7$ ppm. During complexation, only the signal for N1 was shifted 23.7 ppm upfield (Table 2 and Figure 3) and reaches a chemical shift value of $\delta_{\text{N}} -205.0$ ppm. The coordination shift $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{coord}}$ of the pyridinic nitrogen N1 is thus negative (higher shielding of ^{15}N). ^{15}N shieldings have been reported previously for N-metal coordination.^[16] The increase in nitrogen shielding on metal complexation matches earlier observations of similar trends in δ_{N} of metal complexes and parallels the effects induced by alkylation or protonation of a nitrogen lone pair.^[17,18]

Figure 3. Section of the ^1H , ^{15}N -gHMBC 2D NMR spectrum acquired in a 500 MHz spectrometer for a saturated sample (20 mM) of complex **2** in $[\text{D}_6]\text{DMSO}$ at 295 K. Complete data set was acquired in 4 h 33 min for 160-F1 series with a preparation delay optimized for a 7 Hz coupling constant and 80 of number of scans. The gradient ratio was calculated according to the γ values and set to 70:30:50:1.

As a matter of fact, the coordination of pyridines to transition metals such as palladium, platinum, gold, cobalt, rhodium or iridium result in coordination chemical shifts that range from ca. -30 ppm to ca. -150 ppm, and is mainly determined by the type of the central ion and the character of auxiliary ligands in the *trans* position.^[19] The origin of these phenomena is generally attributed to changes in the paramagnetic shielding term, where the relatively small negative nitrogen coordination chemical shift found ($\delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{complex}} < \delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{ligand}}$) are attributable to the stabilization on coordination of both frontier orbitals for the resonant atom, so that the effective ΔE (as arises from the Ramsey formula)^[20] is not greatly changed.^[17,18]

As mentioned earlier, perhaps the most interesting NMR feature in such a complex is that holds an yttrium-89 isotope which is NMR active. In addition, the large chemical shift range reported for this metal nucleus in the range of hundreds ppm, makes it a very good reporter of small changes in its coordination sphere.^[21] The ^{89}Y nucleus combines attractive properties for rapid accessing to NMR data, but at the same time it has important drawbacks such as low receptivity ($D_C = 0.7$) and probably most importantly long T_1 relaxation times due to its negative gyromagnetic constant.^[17,22] The need to use long recovery delays in stand-

ard excitation–acquisition ^{89}Y NMR experiments has been overcome by transferring polarization from ^1H to ^{89}Y via INEPT^[23] and DEPT^[24] schemes, or using inverse detection through proton.^[8,25] Some of us have recently reported its indirect detection from triple resonance experiments employing ^{31}P as the source of polarization.^[15]

One-dimension ^{89}Y NMR spectrum (Figure S10) was acquired over a weekend in order to get the averaged ^{89}Y chemical shift of complex **2**. The signal was located at δ_{Y} 43.8 ppm as a broad singlet with $W_{1/2}$ of ca. 40 Hz. As expected, the exchange between yttrium atoms within the complex produced a large broadness which inhibited its detection through indirect or PT methods. In this sense, all the DEPT and ^1H , ^{89}Y HMQC attempts failed probably due to its very short T_2 times.

Additional insights into the solution structure of **2** were obtained by diffusion studies. The measurement of diffusion constants by pulsed gradient spin-echo (PGSE) NMR methods has recently attracted increasing interest as this technique provides data on molecular volumes and, thus, indirectly on structural characteristics.^[26] In addition, the sequences needed are available in a standard NMR spectrometer, which facilitates the performance of the experiment.

The calculated r_{H} values (by the Stokes–Einstein equation)^[29] assume spherical shapes; hence, they do not represent the real shape of the molecules. Generally, the r_{H} value from the PGSE measurement is in good agreement with that calculated from X-ray data.^[27]

Table 3 shows the PGSE diffusion data for H5Npic (**1**) and **2** in dimethylsulfoxide solution. In the traditional Stejskal–Tanner plots^[28] (Figure 4 and S11), the smaller the attenuation, the lower the diffusion coefficient, and the larger the molecular size. Although the viscosity of the dimethylsulfoxide solutions varies with concentration, we have used the viscosity of the pure solvent for radii calculation. From the measured D values for ligand **1** and complex **2**, we estimated the hydrodynamic radii, r_{H} , to be 3.1 and 6.5 Å, respectively. The results obtained for **1** are in reasonable agreement with the values derived from the X-ray structure, stating that the quality of the crystallographic data are poor. Interestingly, the dissolution of complex **2** in DMSO did not produce any significant change in the r_{H} , with respect to the solid state size, which strongly suggests that complex **2** is not prone to dissociation in DMSO.

Table 3. D and r_{H} values for ligand **1** and the diamagnetic yttrium complex **2** (both at 20 mM) at ambient temperature in $[\text{D}_6]$ -DMSO.

	D ($10^{-10} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$) ^[a]	r_{H} (Å) ^[b]	$r_{\text{X-ray}}$ (Å) ^[c]
H5Npic (1)	3.339 ^[d]	3.1	3.4 ^[e]
DMSO	6.655	1.6	
HDO	8.930	1.2	
2	1.593 ^d	6.5	6.5
DMSO	6.392	1.6	
HDO	8.441	1.2	

[a] The experimental error in the D values is $\pm 2\%$. [b] The viscosity, η , used in the Stokes–Einstein equation is $2.077 \times 10^{-3} \text{ kg m}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The value of η was taken from www.knovel.com. [c] The value was deduced from the X-ray structure by considering the volume of the crystallographic cell divided by Z . Note that this is only an estimate since both molecular structures contain several solvent molecules in the crystal lattice. [d] Average value considering the three aromatic signals monitored. [e] See Supporting Information for X-ray details.

It is important to mention that from Figure 1 one can deduce that complexes **2-3** do not resemble a sphere, so the use of the modified Stokes–Einstein equation could be considered.^[30] In our case, and assuming the shape of our complexes to be cylinders we obtain a shape factor of 1.03 and a c factor of 5.83 which yields a rod-like form with semiaxis of 7.8 and 4.7 Å, which illustrates a more realistic hydrodynamic shape (see Supporting Information).

Figure 4. Stejskal–Tanner plots from ^1H PGSE diffusion experiments in $\text{DMSO}-d_6$ at room temperature, using the stimulated echo sequence, of a saturated solution (20 mM) of complex **2**. The solid lines represent linear least-squares fits to the experimental data. Yellow and blue lines correspond to the attenuation of H_2O and DMSO, respectively.

Magnetic Properties

The alternating-current (ac) magnetic susceptibility measurements were performed as a function of the temperature at different frequencies and applied fields for compound **3**. In the absence of an external field strong frequency dependent in-phase (χ_{M}') and out-of-phase (χ_{M}'') susceptibility signals can be observed below 10 K, indicating the occurrence of SMM behavior (Figure 5).

In general, coordination geometries where the donor atoms are located above and below the equatorial plane as in this case, favor the presence of easy-axis anisotropy on the Dy compounds, and therefore, the presence of SMM behavior.^[31] In addition, as seen in other dinuclear compounds, this behavior is also promoted by the presence of weak exchange interactions between Dy ions, as they reduce the quantum tunneling of the magnetization (QTM) at zero dc field.^[32] However, the tails at low temperatures that appear below the maxima in the χ_{M}' and χ_{M}'' vs. T plots indicate that the QTM is not completely eliminated. The deviation of the relaxation times from linearity also corroborates the existence of other relaxation processes apart from the Orbach mode, while the Cole-Cole plots, with α values in the 0.12 (2 K) – 0.02 (7 K) range, suggest a narrow distribution of slow relaxation at the highest temperatures, compatible with the existence of two processes at the lowest temperatures (Figure 6).

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of in-phase (top) and out-of-phase (bottom) components of the ac susceptibility measured under zero dc field. Inset: Arrhenius plots for the relaxation times. The black and red lines correspond to the best fits to Orbach and Orbach + QTM processes, respectively.

The linear portion of the relaxation times was fitted to the Arrhenius equation, obtaining an effective energy barrier of 40.1 K with $\tau_0 = 7.08 \cdot 10^{-8}$ s. As expected, the effective energy barrier was slightly increased when the simultaneous presence of Orbach and QTM relaxation modes was considered (Equation 1), which led to the following values: $U_{eff} = 50.1$ K, $\tau_0 = 1.81 \cdot 10^{-8}$ s and $\tau_{QTM} = 1.88 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s.

$$\tau^{-1} = \tau_{QTM}^{-1} + \tau_0^{-1} \exp(-U_{eff}/k_B T) \quad (\text{Equation 1})$$

In order to reduce the QTM, an optimal dc field of 3500 Oe was applied (Figure 7). This field was chosen because among the studied ones (from 0 to 3500 Oe), it induces the slowest relaxation (Figure S12).

Figure 6. Cole-Cole plots for **3** under zero (top) and 3500 Oe fields.

However, the tails at low temperatures indicate that the QTM remains operative even at this field, suggesting that the QTM is promoted by intermolecular magnetic dipolar interactions. Although the intermolecular interactions and therefore, the QTM, could be eliminated by preparing diluted samples with Y(III), the co-crystallization of **2** with isostructural diamagnetic complex **3** via solvothermal synthetic routes could not be easily controlled.

After the application of the external field, the Cole-Cole plots lead to higher α values found in the 0.47 (3.2 K) – 0.11 (6.8 K) range, indicating the existence of several relaxation modes (Figure 6). The best fit of the relaxation times was obtained when considering the simultaneous presence of Orbach and Raman processes between 3.2 and 6.8 K (Equation 2), obtaining the following fitting parameters: $U_{eff} = 92.0$ K, $\tau_0 = 8.47 \cdot 10^{-11}$ s, $b = 4.38$ and $n = 4.43$. In general, $n = 9$ is for Kramers ions,^[33] but depending on the structure of the levels, n values between 1 and 6 can be considered as reasonable.^[34] The Arrhenius fit of the high-temperature data led to U_{eff} and τ_0 values of 51.0 K and $1.47 \cdot 10^{-8}$ s, respectively.

Figure 7. Temperature dependence of in-phase (top) and out-of-phase (bottom) components of the ac susceptibility measured under 3500 Oe applied dc field. Inset: Arrhenius plots for the relaxation times. The black and blue lines correspond to the best fits to Orbach and Orbach + Raman processes, respectively.

These results seem to indicate that the Raman relaxation process significantly affects the Orbach relaxation mode, which reduces the thermal energy barrier for the magnetization reversal. Finally, it should be noted that although QTM is not considered in these fits, the tails observed in the χ_M' and χ_M'' vs. T plots strongly suggest its presence at the lowest temperatures.

$$\tau^{-1} = BT^n + \tau_0^{-1} \exp(-U_{eff}/k_B T) \quad (\text{Equation 2})$$

Conclusions

Two new air-stable dysprosium and yttrium compounds based on a 5-nitro-2-picolinic carboxylate were prepared and structurally characterized. The solid-state structures were established by single-crystal X-ray diffraction. MS of these compounds proved the retention of the metal core when dissolved in polar media. To further confirm the dinuclear nature in solution, PGSE diffusion measurements on the diamagnetic Yttrium complex **2** were carried out and revealed that it is stable in solution. In addition, full ^1H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N , ^{89}Y , $\Delta^1\text{H}_{\text{coord}}$, $\Delta^{13}\text{C}_{\text{coord}}$ and $\Delta^{15}\text{N}_{\text{coord}}$ data are given providing, through the analysis of the Ramsey equation, the first electronic insights of these derivatives. Importantly, Dysprosium material exhibits SMM behavior with frequency dependence of the out-of-phase susceptibility at zero dc field. To the best of our knowledge, these are the first coordination compounds synthesized with 5-nitro-2-picolinic acid demonstrating that the use of this linker by hydrothermal routes is an excellent strategy for generating novel materials with interesting physical properties such as magnetism.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information

Supporting information for this article is given via a link at the end of the document. The Supporting Information (18 figures and 3 tables) is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website. Experimental procedures, spectral and crystallographic data (PDF).

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NOTES

Crystallographic data for **2** (CIF). Crystallographic data for **3** (CIF). CCDC numbers 1508449-1508450.

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Novel air-stable coordination compounds based on a 5-nitro-2-picolinic carboxylate have been synthesized and characterized. Dysprosium-based complex exhibits SMM behavior with frequency dependence of the out-of-phase susceptibility at zero dc field. High resolution MS (ESI) and diffusion NMR experiments suggest that the dinuclear skeleton of these compounds is robust and maintained in solution.

